

Some less understood concepts in kinetics and mechanism

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Abstract : Less understood concepts in kinetics and mechanism like 'Role of stoichiometry in deriving different rates', Fallacy in the application of 'Law of Mass Action to Rates and Chemical Equilibrium', 'Misconception about zero order reaction', 'Reaction - scheme and Mechanism' and 'Concentration and time orders, and Mechanism' are described and explained.

Keywords : Chemical education.

During teaching of forty years, I came across several instances of concepts in kinetics and mechanism which were less understood or not well understood by the teachers and students. There may be three reasons for this. Firstly, some of the concepts have not been mentioned in the chapter on kinetics in books of Physical Chemistry although the concepts are elementary. Secondly, treatment of the concepts in some of the books is not appropriate. Thirdly, a few of the concepts are inter-disciplinary and require a little more care in elaboration of the subject.

(A) Role of stoichiometry in deriving differential rate for different order-equations

Text books of physical chemistry with a chapter on kinetics or even a book on kinetics with only one exception¹, seem to over-simplify the concept of order while discussing differential equations of different orders and their integration². Treatment of this subject for a first order reaction starts as,

for a second order reaction as

and for a third order reaction as

A misconception implicit in the above statement is that the coefficients of A, B and C also represent the number of molecules involved in the stoichiometry of the reactions.

In absence of any qualified statement, a student learning kinetics for the first time gets the impression that stoichiometry is not different from the order. In fact they are quite different.

It is always better to write stoichiometric quantities of reactants in the equation and then mention about the order. If we have a general second order eq. (4)

with n_1 moles of A reacting with n_2 moles of B (stoichiometry) and the order being one in each A and B, the differential equation for the disappearance of A is given by (5),

$$-d[A]/dt = k(a-x)(b - (n_2/n_1)x) \quad (5)$$

'a' and 'b' are the initial concentrations of A and B respectively and 'x' is the concentration of A disappearing in time 't'. The equation is of same form as one would obtain from (2a) i.e.

$$-d[A]/dt = k(a-x)(b-x) \quad (6)$$

where 'k' is the rate constant and this on integration gives the well known eq. (7)

$$kt = \frac{1}{(a-b)} \ln \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)} \quad (7)$$

However, one has to appreciate that (7) is a special case of general eq. (5) when $n_1 = n_2$. Eq. (8) follows from (5)

$$\frac{dx}{(a-x)(b - (n_2/n_1)x)} = kdt \quad (8)$$

This on integration would give (9)

$$kt = \frac{n_1}{n_2a - n_1b} \ln \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b - (n_2/n_1)x)} \quad (9)$$

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If $n_1 = n_2$, one obtains eq. (7). However, eq. (9) is general and is applicable to a reaction of second order in which the two reactants have separately the order of one.

Thus the order can never be indicated by the coefficient of formulae of any reactant in a stoichiometric equation. It is an experimental entity. A reaction represented by (4) can well be third order, first order in A and second order in B, or second order in A and first order in B, so that the total order is three. Likewise it can be of any order.

Stoichiometry has a role while calculating the second order rate constant derived from a pseudo-first order rate constant when one of the reactants is present in excess concentration. In general the pseudo-first order rate constant is divided by the concentration of reactant present in excess to calculate the second order rate constant irrespective of the stoichiometry of the reaction. The second order rate constant is a constant anyway, but its value may not be true. If A is present in excess in eq. (9), one obtains,

$$kt = \frac{n_1}{n_2 a} \ln \frac{b}{(b - (n_2/n_1)x)} \quad (10)$$

This is typical of first order reaction. In all such cases a plot of $\log (b - (n_2/n_1)x)$ (and not simply $\log (b - x)$ versus time should be made to obtain the pseudo-first order rate constant. This should be divided by (n_2/n_1) (and not simply 'a') to obtain the true second order rate constant. Thus the pseudo-first order plots and the derived second order rate constant depend on the stoichiometry of the reaction. It should be appreciated that eq. (10) has been obtained by following the kinetics by determining the reactant which is not in excess.

Calculation of true rate constant from the pseudo-first order rate constant :

A second order reaction³, $S_2O_8^{2-} + 2I^- = 2SO_4^{2-} + I_2$, which is first order in $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and first order in I^- , has a rate law similar to (9) i.e.

$$kt = \frac{n_1}{n_2[S_2O_8^{2-}] - n_1[I^-]} \ln \frac{[I^-][S_2O_8^{2-} - x]}{[S_2O_8^{2-}] - [I^- - (n_2/n_1)x]} \quad (11)$$

If $[S_2O_8^{2-}] \gg [I^-]$ and the reaction is followed by determining iodide from time to time.

$$\begin{aligned} k't &= \frac{n_1}{n_2[S_2O_8^{2-}]} \ln \frac{[I^-]}{[I^- - (n_2/n_1)x]} \\ &= \frac{1}{2[S_2O_8^{2-}]} \ln \frac{[I^-]}{[I^- - 2x]} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

If 'k' is the true second order rate constant, pseudo-first order rate constant,

$$k' = 2k [S_2O_8^{2-}] \quad (13)$$

$$\text{and hence } k = k'/2[S_2O_8^{2-}] \quad (14)$$

If $[I^-] \gg [S_2O_8^{2-}]$ and the reaction is followed by estimating $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$,

$$\begin{aligned} k't &= \frac{1}{[I^-]} \ln \frac{[I^-][S_2O_8^{2-} - x]}{[S_2O_8^{2-}][I^- - 2x]} \\ &= \frac{1}{[I^-]} \ln \frac{[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{[S_2O_8^{2-} - x]} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

$$\text{and hence } k' = k [I^-] \text{ and } k = k'/[I^-] \quad (16)$$

Thus the calculation of true second order rate constant from pseudo-first order rate constant depends on stoichiometry of the reaction. It is also clear from the following Table 1.

Table 1. Calculation of true second order rate constant from pseudo-first order rate constant

$[S_2O_8^{2-}]$	$[I^-]$	$10^5 k'$	$10^3 k =$	$10^3 k =$
(M)	(M)	(s ⁻¹)	$10^3 k'/[I^-]$	$10^3 k'/2[S_2O_8^{2-}]$
			(M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	(M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
0.001	0.01	5.4	5.4	–
0.001	0.02	11.0	5.5	–
0.001	0.03	16.2	5.4	–
0.01	0.0002	10.8	–	5.4
0.005	0.0002	5.3	–	5.3
0.002	0.0002	2.2	–	5.5

(B) Fallacy in the application of Law of Mass Action to rates and Chemical Equilibrium

The subject of Chemical Equilibrium is of great importance for an understanding of chemical reactions. It is introduced to students at an early stage through the Law of Mass Action stated by Guldberg and Waage⁴ in 1863 which deals with rates of reactions. Many textbooks of Physical Chemistry and/or General Chemistry start with the Law of Mass Action and then rates of reactions to define the state of equilibrium. This approach not only misguides⁵ students but makes understanding of Chemical Kinetics difficult at a later stage.

The subject is developed with an example of a simple reversible reaction (1)

and then equating the rates of forward and backward reactions in the equilibrium state. The rates are defined by the Law of Mass Action as,

$$\text{Rate of forward reaction} = k_1 [A]_e [B]_e \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Rate of backward reaction} = k_{-1} [C]_e [D]_e \quad (3)$$

Subscript 'e' denotes equilibrium concentrations but from here onwards it has not been used and concentrations within square brackets are equilibrium concentrations. For another general reversible reaction (4), we have

$$\text{Rate of forward reaction} = k_4 [A]^{n_1} [B]^{n_2} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Rate of backward reaction} = k_{-4} [C]^{n_3} [D]^{n_4} \quad (6)$$

where A and B are reactants and C and D are products and k_1 and k_4 , and k_{-1} and k_{-4} are respectively the rate constant for the forward and backward reactions. The equilibrium constant K_1 and K_4 are defined as,

$$K_1 = \frac{[C][D]}{[A][B]} = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}} \quad (7)$$

$$K_4 = \frac{[C]^{n_3}[D]^{n_4}}{[A]^{n_1}[B]^{n_2}} = \frac{k_4}{k_{-4}} \quad (8)$$

The fallacy is that the rate of reaction is not defined but the Law of Mass Action is defined through these equilibrium rates. It appears from above that once we know the equilibrium eqs. (1) and (4), it is possible to write down the rate eqs. (2), (3), (5) and (6) without carrying out the rate experiments, which is not correct. Laws of Chemical Equilibrium (7) and (8) and the equilibrium constants K_1 and K_4 have been written, and rightly so, on the basis of Law of Mass Action. The point will be clear from the following reversible reaction^{6,7},

One can no doubt write down the equilibrium constant K_9 straightway on the basis of eq. (9),

$$K_9 = \frac{[H_3AsO_3][I_3^-]}{[H_3AsO_4][I^-]^3[H^+]^2} \quad (10)$$

The point to be understood is whether we obtain the equilibrium equation from the two rates or we obtain rates from the equilibrium equation. It is from the rates that we have equilibrium equation and the rates cannot be known as such from the Law of Mass Action without carrying out the actual rate experiments. The point is made clear further in the following lines. Can we write down following rates of reactions from equilibrium (9).

$$\text{Rate of forward action} = d[I_3^-]/dt = k_9[H_3AsO_4][I^-]^3[H^+]^2 ?$$

$$\text{Rate of backward reaction} = -d[I_3^-]/dt = k_{-9}[H_3AsO_3][I_3^-] ?$$

No we cannot do so. The actual rate eqs. (11) and (12) are obtained by doing rate experiments.

$$d[I_3^-]/dt = k_9[H_3AsO_4][H^+][I^-] \quad (11)$$

$$-d[I_3^-]/dt = k_{-9}[H_3AsO_3][I_3^-]/[I^-]^2[H^+] \quad (12)$$

Now if these two equations are equated as per Law of Equilibrium, we get the same correct result for K_9 as we obtain from equations with question mark (?). Since the same correct result (eq. (10)) is obtained by wrong procedure (i.e. from equations with question mark) as well as from the correct procedure (eqs. (11) and (12)), this fact has been hiding the weakness of the Law of Mass Action prompting one to write the rate equations directly from equilibrium eq. (9). In any case the correct procedure is to obtain eqs. (11) and (12) from actual experiments and equate them to obtain equilibrium eq. (10). Once we have determined this rate dependence with respect to each of the reactants, we can apply Law of Mass Action, we can write down the products of various functions of concentrations to know the rate as has been done in rate eqs. (5) and (6) and then to obtain the equilibrium eq. (4) by equating (5) and (6).

The fallacy in the application of Law of Mass Action arises from the fact that equilibrium (9) is not a combination of simple straight forward reactions. It has complex mechanism. If we know the mechanism (the elementary steps) we can apply the Law of Mass Action to the rate determining step to obtain the correct result for equilibrium constant. HNO_2 decomposes in aqueous solution as,

with the following mechanism.

Reaction (13) is complex and hence we cannot apply the Law of Mass Action to this, but we can do so in reaction (16) which is elementary and rate controlling. Thus from eq. (16) we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate of forward reaction} &= d[NO_3^-]/dt = k_{16}[N_2O_4] \\ &= k_{16}K_{15}[NO_2]^2 \\ &= k_{16}K_{15}K_{14}^2[HNO_2]^4/P_{NO}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate of backward reaction} &= -d[NO_3^-]/dt \\ &= k_{-16}[NO_3^-][H^+][HNO_2] \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

On equating (17) and (18), we get the value of K_{13}

$$\frac{[NO_3^-][H^+][P_{NO}^2]}{[HNO_2]^3} = \frac{k_{16}k_{14}^2k_{15}}{k_{-16}} = K_{13} \quad (19)$$

which is what one can obtain directly from eq. (13).

The Law of Mass Action also fails in several instances where rate is inversely proportional to the concentration of a reactant. In the oxidation of nitrite⁸ with thallic perchlorate in acid solution, the rate is inversely proportional to the concentration of nitrite for its large concentration range. The reaction occurs as,

and the rate is,

$$d[\text{TI}^{\text{III}}]/dt = \frac{k_2 K_2 [\text{TI}^{\text{III}}] [\text{HNO}_2] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_2 [\text{H}^+] [\text{HNO}_2] + K_2 K_3 [\text{HNO}_2]^2} \quad (21)$$

corresponding to the following mechanism,

It is obvious from the rate law and the mechanism that for large concentrations of the reactant HNO_2 the rate is inhibited. This is against Law of Mass Action. Only complex $\text{TI}(\text{NO}_2)_2^+$ is reactive and step (25) is rate controlling and the law can be applied to this step and not to the overall complex reaction step (20).

(C) Misconception about zero order reaction

There cannot be a zero order reaction unless it is a gaseous chain or surface reaction. Even then it would depend on the pressure of the gas or nature of surface of the vessel. In solution rate has to depend on one of the reactant-concentrations but even then there might be conditions under which reaction may appear to be zero order. Iodination of acetone (1) is one such example⁹.

with the following mechanism (2) and (3) and rate law (4),

$$-d[\text{I}_2]/dt = k[\text{H}^+][\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3] \quad (4)$$

The reaction is first order in acetone and in H^+ , and zero order in iodine since rate does not depend on the concentration of

iodine. The rate of formation of enol is thus first order and it is used up as soon as formed according to step (3). It is convenient to follow the kinetics by titrating remaining iodine with thiosulphate and iodine thus consumed gives the concentration of enol formed at any time. This decrease in iodine concentration is first order but one cannot make a plot with respect to a function of the concentration of iodine against time ($\log(a-x)$ versus time). If we do so, what value of 'a' (initial concentration) for iodine is to be employed for calculation of $(a-x)$ though 'x' at different time are known? No value of 'a' can be employed. In fact one should calculate the concentration of acetone at different times and then make a plot. If 'a' is the initial concentration of acetone and 'x' is the molar concentration of iodine consumed at any time 't' ($a-x$) is the remaining molar concentration of acetone at any time 't'. Since acetone has first order dependence, $\log(a-x)$ versus time would give a straight line. However, if 'a' is much larger than 'x' a plot of $(a-x)$ versus time would also give a straight line giving an impression that the order in acetone is zero, but this does not represent zero order character of reaction because if this plot is made for sufficiently large decrease in acetone-concentration, one would obtain a normal curve characteristic of first order. Although concentration of acetone may be large or much larger than that of iodine but we cannot talk of pseudo-zero order in acetone. It is always first order. One should never make a plot in terms of any function of the concentration of iodine versus time since rate is independent of the concentration of iodine¹⁰.

Osmium(VIII) catalyzed oxidation of pyridine with hexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline solution is a reaction¹¹, rate of which does not depend on the concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III), and also on the concentration of pyridine for its large concentrations but it is not a zero order reaction. The rate is monitored by the concentration of osmium(VIII) either present in traces in the chemicals as impurity or added in small quantities ($10^{-7}M$) to the reaction mixture. It has a complex rate-dependence on hydroxide ion-concentration. It has following reaction-scheme ((5), (6) and (7)) and rate law (8) at fixed $[\text{OH}^-]$.

$$-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]/dt = \frac{kK[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][\text{Py}]}{1 + K[\text{Py}]} \quad (8)$$

$$= k[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] \text{ at large } [\text{Py}]$$

The reaction appears to be zero order since rate is independent of the concentrations of the main reactants but it is not a zero order reaction.

(D) Reaction-scheme and mechanism

The two terms 'reaction-scheme' and 'mechanism' are synonymously used, one for the other without making any distinction. However, there is a subtle difference¹² between them.

- (i) A reaction-scheme is a bunch of several steps occurring simultaneously and/or consecutively. The mechanism may be defined as a detailed and pictorial representation of the reaction itself.
- (ii) Gross reactants and intermediates form part of the reaction-scheme, but the exact nature of these species form part of the mechanism.
- (iii) The information about the reaction-scheme is provided by the kinetics but the mechanism is known from spectroscopic and other physical methods in addition to kinetic analysis.

The mechanism should answer questions such as what are the active sites of the reactants? What properties do they exhibit? Are they donors or acceptors? Which of the bonds are broken or formed? What is identity of the intermediates?

- (iv) A reaction-scheme is almost firmly established. At best it can be enlarged to accommodate additional facts and evidences. A mechanism on the other hand, which is based on current theories of structure and bonding, may be altogether disproven.
- (v) Kinetics gives the composition of the activated complex but physical methods provide the structure of the activated/transition state.
- (vi) In terms of reaction-scheme the achievements of kinetics can be recognized. In terms of mechanism, it is the limitations of kinetics rather than its merits which are highlighted.

R. S. Nyholm¹³ has rightly said 'Kinetics to Mechanism equals facts to fiction'.

One appropriate example of a reaction¹⁴ with the reaction-scheme and mechanism both, is the oxidation of hydroxylamine with Fe^{III} in acetate buffers in diffused sunlight.

On the basis of kinetic results and stoichiometry, following reaction-scheme was suggested.

The rate law is :

$$-d[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]/dt = \frac{k_1 k_3 [\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}][\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+][\text{H}^+]}{k_2 [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}] + k_3 [\text{H}^+]} \quad (4)$$

However, from this reaction-scheme no information is available about the reactive species of Fe^{III}, about any complex formation between Fe^{III} and NH₂OH, about involvement of any intermediates and about the stoichiometry and products under different conditions. Information about these details leading to mechanism is obtained from the following.

- (i) Stoichiometry and products are different for the reaction occurring in dark.

$$2\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} + \text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+ \rightarrow 2\text{Fe}^{\text{II}} + 1/2\text{N}_2\text{O} + 3\text{H}^+ + 1/2\text{H}_2\text{O} \quad (5)$$
- (ii) Both N₂ and N₂O are formed in partially dark reaction conditions.
- (iii) UV spectroscopy of the two reactions reveals two intermediate complexes absorbing at different wavelengths – at 291 nm for the light sensitive reaction having a small molar extinction coefficient and at 341 nm for the dark reaction having a very large molar extinction coefficient.
- (iv) The stoichiometry of the two reactions is same i.e. 1 : 1 in the presence of acrylamide and no gaseous products are obtained.
- (v) 99% of Fe^{III} is present as oxo-centered-trimeric species in acetate buffers.
- (vi) The three different methods of analysis – volumetric analysis of Fe^{III}, gas analysis of N₂O and UV absorption spectroscopic analysis at 291 nm or 341 nm gave identical results.

On the basis of above information following mechanism was suggested.

Mechanism of Fe^{III} and NH₃OH⁺ reaction in acetate buffers.

Fig. 1. Spectra of reaction mixture after different times : $[Tl^{III}] = 8.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; $[SCN^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[HClO_4] = 2.0 M$, Ref. . $2.0 M HClO_4$.

Another example where the reaction-scheme is supported and refined to mechanism by the physical methods is the oxidation¹⁵ of thiocyanate with thallium(III) in acid perchlorate solutions.

The reaction is complicated and only incomplete reaction-scheme could be known from the kinetic results, though kinetics did provide lot of information which in conjunction with spectroscopic results gave the mechanism. When $[SCN^-]_0 \gg [Tl^{III}]_0$, the rate was second order in $[Tl^{III}]$ according to the rate law $-d[Tl^{III}]/dt = k_2[Tl^{III}]^2$. Thiocyanate dependence under the same condition was as per eq. (7)

$$k_2 = C/(1 + D[SCN^-])^2 \quad (7)$$

where C and D are constants depending on various concentrations. When $[Tl^{III}]_0 \gg [SCN^-]_0$, the order in $[SCN^-]$ is also two and the observed rate law is as in eq. (8).

$$-d[Tl^{III}]/dt = E[SCN^-]^2/(1 + F[Tl^{III}])^2 \quad (8)$$

where E and F are constants depending on various concentrations. However, the overall order is not four but two. When $[Tl^{III}]_0 = [SCN^-]_0$, the observed rate law is (9).

$$-d[Tl^{III}]/dt = A[Tl^{III}]^2 \text{ or } A[SCN^-]^2 \quad (9)$$

All these results strongly suggest the formation of three complexes, $Tl_2(SCN)^{5+}$, $Tl(SCN)^{2+}$ and $HTl(SCN)_2^{2+}$ including the inverse hydrogen-ion dependence when $[SCN^-]_0 \gg [Tl^{III}]_0$ and the only reactive 1 : 1 complex seems to have an order of two through the formation of a dimer.

When $[Tl^{III}]_0 \gg [SCN^-]_0$, in the initial stages of the reaction (0.5, 2, 6 and 15 min), peaks at 196, 231, 250 nm are obtained (Fig. 1). The last two peaks ultimately disappear and a peak

(214 nm) characteristic of Tl^I appears. The peak at 196 nm corresponds to Tl^{III} and those at 231 nm and 250 nm must correspond to one or two intermediate species. The peak at 250 nm can be ascribed to 1 : 1 complex. The shoulder at 231 nm corresponds to thiocyanogen.

Based on these results and also hydrogen-ion dependence, following mechanism was suggested.

(E) Concentration and time orders and mechanism

Few kineticists make use of both the orders to know the mechanism¹⁶. Most of them use one and regard the other to be same, and in fact in most cases the two are not different and hence the importance of a distinction between them is lost sight of. However, it is always better to first determine the concentration order and then obtain the kinetic parameters by making use of time order. The concentration order is determined by carrying out the experiments with different concentrations of the reactant, obtaining initial rates by the plane mirror method¹⁷, and by making log-log plot of the initial rate and the concentration. The slope of the resulting straight

Fig. 2. Concentration and time plots and determination of initial rate.

line gives the order as shown in Fig. 2. As a matter of fact this is true order from which the rate law can be derived. Such an order is free of the effect of product-auto inhibition or auto catalysis. Time order shows rate dependence of the concentration of reactant during the course of reaction. It is generally known by substituting the concentration of a reactant

at different times in the differential equations of various orders and obtaining near constant values of the rate constants, but the better method is to obtain instantaneous rates at different times in a single run and process the data as in case of concentration order as shown in Fig. 3. This rate-dependence (time order) may or may not change during the interval the observations are made. If there is no change, the two orders are same and the reaction may have a simple mechanism. If time order changes or it is different than the concentration order, the reaction is complicated¹⁸ and one has to be careful in writing out the mechanism and deriving the rate law. One reason for this type of complication is the effect of the concentration of one of the products but other factors may also be responsible for the complex behaviour.

Oxidation¹⁹ of iron(II) with thallium(III) in aqueous perchloric acid solutions illustrates the point of view mentioned above. Following mechanism has been suggested for the reaction.

The rate law is :

Three different initial concentrations in three different experiments and initial rates.

Three different initial concentrations in the same run and instantaneous rates.

Plot of log (IR) vs log C to know the order of reaction.

(IR) Initial or instantaneous rate = kC^n (n is the order and k is the rate constant) $\log(\text{IR}) = \log k + n \log C$

Fig. 3. Determination of order from initial and instantaneous rates.

$$-d[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]/dt = \frac{k_1 K_3 [\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}] [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]^2}{k_2 [\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] + k_3 [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]} \quad (3)$$

In the initial stages of the reaction, no Fe^{III} is present and hence the rate law will reduce to (4) with first order dependence on each of Fe^{II} and Tl^{III} ,

$$d[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]/dt = k_1 [\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}] [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}] \quad (4)$$

If 'a' and 'b' are the initial concentrations of Fe^{II} and Tl^{III} , and 2x is the concentration of Fe^{III} formed at any time 't', a second order plot of $\log((a - 2x)/(b - x))$ versus time would initially give a straight line turning subsequently into a curve after about 50% reaction. Such a change occurs because the product Fe^{III} appears in sufficient quantities after 50% reaction and rate law (3) holds. This shows the order in Fe^{II} to increase. Thus the order in Fe^{II} changes even during the course of reaction. Any determination of order with respect to Fe^{II} may not be possible or it may not be one or two but between one and two.

A reaction²⁰ similar in mechanism and with almost similar rate law is the oxidation of Cr^{III} with Ce^{IV} in acid perchlorate solutions, but with a difference that the reactant Ce^{IV} (corresponding to Fe^{II} of the previous example) does not appear in the denominator. Reaction occurs as follows :

Mechanism and rate law are :

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = \frac{3kk_6[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]^2[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}]}{[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]} \quad (k_6/k_{-6} = k) \quad (9)$$

If the reaction were to behave just like the previous one, rate law (10) would have been obtained.

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = \frac{3kk_6[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]^2[\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}]}{k_6[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] + k_{-6}[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]} \quad (10)$$

However, for this reaction $k_{-6}[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}] \gg k_6[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ and hence the first term of the denominator is neglected giving rate law (9). Hence, this reaction is clear cut first order in Cr^{III} , second order in Ce^{IV} and inverse first order in Ce^{III} . In the previous example had the term $k_2[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] \gg k_3[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]$, one would have obtained a rate law similar to (9).

Yet another reaction²¹ depicting the change in the concentration order (and not time order) for the large

concentration of a reactant is the oxidation of hydrazine with Fe^{III} in acid perchlorate solutions occurring as follows.

If Fe^{II} is not present (i.e. for lower concentrations of Fe^{III}) order in Fe^{III} is one, but it shows deviation from the first order in the higher concentration range. Hydrazine-order is also one if no Fe^{II} or small concentration of Fe^{II} is present, but it becomes greater than one in the presence of Fe^{II} . As a matter of fact the reaction is first order in each Fe^{III} and N_2H_5^+ for their lower concentrations. Following are mechanism and rate law.

$$-d[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]/dt = \frac{K_H k_1 k_3 [\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] [\text{N}_2\text{H}_5^+]^2}{[\text{H}^+] (k_2 [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}] + k_3 [\text{N}_2\text{H}_5^+])} \quad (15)$$

If $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]$ is small, rate law reduces to (16)

$$-d[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]/dt = \frac{K_H k_1 [\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] [\text{N}_2\text{H}_5^+]^2}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (16)$$

At large Fe^{III} , formation of Fe^{II} becomes significant and the denominator tends to reduce the rate and a plot of rate versus $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]$ deviates from the straight line. Second order in $[\text{N}_2\text{H}_5^+]$ at large $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]$ could not be shown because the reaction becomes very slow on account of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}]$ being in the denominator.

Chain reactions occur with a complicated mechanism and they also illustrate the difference between the two types of orders. In the thermal decomposition of acetaldehyde²², the concentration order (true order) was found to be 3/2 but the order with respect to time being greater than the order with respect to concentration, means that as the reaction proceeds, rate falls off more rapidly than it would be expected to do on the basis of true order. Thus after the reactant concentration has fallen to one half of the initial value, rate would have fallen to a value $(1/2)^{3/2}$ of the initial value on the basis of concentration order. The time order is two resulting in large decrease in rate. This large following off of the rate means that some intermediate is inhibiting the reaction.

Similarly less falling off of rate expected from the concentration order can be explained by the fact that the time order is less than the concentration order. It is therefore advisable to know both these orders for a reaction in order to obtain rate law and propose a mechanism.

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